

Anti-Histamine Action of a Shenbagapoo Kuligai

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ABSTRACT

Siddhars found a foremost traditional system of medicine called siddha system of medicine. According to this system diseases are recognized based on vatha, pitha and kapha. The medicines are prepared using the ingredients of three main categories of natural origin. They are thavaram [herbs], thathu [metals and minerals] and jeevam [animals]. **Shenbaga poo kuligai** is a classical siddha drug used for treating **Mantham**. Mantham is a paediatric illness. **Suzhi Mantham** is one of the types of mantham under 21 types. Suzhi Mantham is a respiratory disease followed by indigestion having symptoms of intermittent fever, cough, wheezing, difficulty in breathing, rib retraction, loss of appetite and sleeplessness. Shenbagapoo kuligai is a traditional drug used for treating suzhi mantham, so the author has done an antihistamine study for the shenbaga poo kuligai. From this study the test drug antagonises the effect of histamine when added together.

KEYWORDS: antihistamine, shenbagapoo kuligai, preclinical study, suzhi mantham.

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AIM

The aim of this preclinical study is to evaluate the antihistamine activity of a trial drug Shenbagapoo kuligai in treatment of suzhi mantham without any side effects and to create awareness about the siddha system of medicine to the world.

STUDY PLACE

The study was carried out in KM College of pharmacy in Madurai.

RAW DRUG COLLECTION

Raw drugs of shenbaga poo kuligai are collected in pharmacy of Government Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai.

INGREDIENTS OF A TRAIL DRUG

SHENBAGAPOO KULIGAI

S.No	Botanical Name/English Name	Tamil Name
1	Michelia champaca	Shenbagam
2	Saussurea lappa	Kostam
3	Plectranthus amboinicus	Vilamichaiver
4	Elettaria cardamomum	Ealam
5	Fel bovinum purifactum	Korosanai
6	Ferruginous shale	Sathra bedi

7	Glycyrrhiza glabra	Adhimadhuram
8	Vetiveria zizanioides	Vetiver
9	Artemisia nilagirica	Masipachiai

METHOD OF PREPARATION

The siddha formulation shenbagapoo kuligai is prepared as per SOP in Government Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai. All the raw drugs are collected, properly identified and purified according to the purification process of each drug. They are made into powder and grinded smoothly using the juice of vetiver stem, and then the mixture is made into tablet form and allowed to dry and properly stored.

ANTI-HISTAMINE STUDY OF SHENBAGA POO KULIGAI ON ISOLATED GUINEA PIG ILEUM

AIM:

To find out the Anti-histamine effect of Shenbaga Poo Kuligai on isolated Guinea Pig ileum (Burn-1952)

Anti-Histamine Action of a Shenbagapoo Kuligai

PREPARATION OF THE TEST DRUG

1 gm of Shenbaga Poo Kuligai was dissolved in 10ml of water. Then it was used for the experiment.

SOLUTIONS REQUIRED

- Histamine -1 in 100000 strength
- Anti-histamine - (Pheniramine Maleate) 2.5 mg /ml
- Test drug -Shenbaga Poo Kuligai 100mg/ml

NUTRIENT SOLUTION

S.I No	Solution	Quantity
1	Tyrode solution	1 to 2 liters
2	Tyrode solution	1 litre
3	NaCl	8gms
4	KCl	0.2 gms
5	CaCl ₂	0.2 gms
6	MgSo ₄	0.26 gms
7	NaH ₂ PO ₄	0.05 gms
8	NaHCO ₃	1 gms
9	Glucose	1 gms

TISSUE USED

Guinea Pig ileum

APPARATUS REQUIRED

Student's organ bath, Sherrington rotating drum, Scissors, Cotton thread etc.

PROCEDURE

An overnight fasted Guinea Pig weighing about 400 grams was sacrificed by a blow on the head and carotid bleeding. The abdomen was suddenly opened and ileocaecal junction was found out. A small piece of ideal portion was cut and removed and placed in a dish containing warm aerated Tyrode solution. The contents of lumen of ileum was gently rinsed by pushing Tyrode solution into it. 3cm length segment was cut from this part of ileum, and was tied with thread on both ends separately without closing the lumen and the tissue was mounted in an organ bath containing Tyrode solution maintained at 37°C and bubbled with air by oxygen tube.

First the rotating drum was allowed to run for 1 minute to record the baseline. Drugs were given to study the inhibiting effect of Histamine. 0.1ml of Histamine was added and the drum was allowed to run for 30 seconds. Thus the tissue was standardized and then the drum was stopped and the Acetyl Choline was washed out.

Again Tyrode solution was added to the organ bath till the level comes to the baseline. The drum was allowed to run for 1 minute. To the organ-bath, 1 ml of test drug was added, waited for one minute. To the organ-bath, 1ml of test

drug was added, waited for one minute and 0.1 ml of Histamine was added and the drum was allowed to run for 30 seconds to record the inhibitory action of the test drug. Again the recording were repeated by adding 0.1 ml of Antihistamine and 0.2ml Histamine and the drum was allowed to run for 30 seconds to record the antagonistic action of Anti-histamine.

INFERENCE

From the study it is inferred that the test drug antagonize the effect of Effect of Histamine when added together. So the drug Shenbaga Poo Kuligai as got significant Anti- histamine activity.

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